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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON VACCINE DEVELOPMENT - A
SAFEGUARDING KEY FOR GLOBAL HEALTH****Miss. Vungarala Akhila¹, Mr. V. S. Chandrasekaran^{2*}, Dr. K. Venugopal³**¹Final year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.**Abstract:**

Vaccines are biological preparations that provides active immunity against specific diseases, utilizing weakened or inactivated microorganisms, toxins, or mRNA. Vaccination is the process of administering vaccines to enhance the body's immune response. Immunization refers to making a person resistant to infectious diseases. Various vaccine types exist, including live, attenuated, and inactivated vaccines, among others. The history of vaccines spans centuries, beginning with Edward Jenner's smallpox vaccine in 1796 and advancing to modern developments like the COVID-19 vaccine in 2020. Vaccine manufacturing involves selecting strains, growing microorganisms, isolating and purifying them, inactivating them, formulating the vaccine, and conducting quality control. The process of producing vaccines is complex, but crucial to public health and disease prevention. The administration routes include oral, intranasal, subcutaneous, and intramuscular methods. Finally, extensive testing ensures safety and efficacy, with performance monitoring for side effects post-vaccination, highlighting the importance of vaccines in public health.

KEY WORDS: Vaccine, Immunization, Manufacturing Process, Formulation Components, Quality Control and Testing.

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1.INTRODUCTION:

VACCINE:

A vaccine is a biological preparation that provides active acquired immunity to a particular infectious or malignant disease. vaccine is a suspension of weakened, killed or fragmented microorganisms or toxins or other biological preparation such as those consisting of antibodies, lymphocytes or mRNA that is administered primarily to prevent disease.

VACCINATION:

The administration of vaccine is called as vaccination .vaccination a simple, safe, and effective way of protecting you against harmful diseases, before you come into contact with them. It uses your body's natural defence to build resistance to specific infections and makes your immune system stronger.

IMMUNIZATION:

Immunization is the process whereby a person is made immune or resistant to an infectious disease, typically by the administration of a vaccine.

2.TYPES OF VACCINES:

- Live, attenuated vaccines.
- Inactivated (killed vaccines)
- Subunit vaccines.
- Toxoids vaccines.
- mRNA vaccines.
- Viral vector vaccines.

3.HISTORY OF VACCINES:

Edward Jenner coined the term vaccine and vaccination. He discovers **the smallpox** vaccine by inoculating a young boy with cowpox. The word vaccine comes from the Latin word "Vacca", which means cow.

18th century

- 1796 – Edward Jenner develops and documents first vaccine for smallpox.

19th century

- 1885 – First vaccine for rabies by Louis Pasteur and Émile Roux

20th century

- 1952 – First intravenous vaccine for polio
- 1963 – First vaccine for measles
- 1967 – First vaccine for mumps
- 1970 – First vaccine for rubella

21st century

- 2020 – First vaccine for COVID-19

4. ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION:

ORAL ROUTE: Oral vaccine is administered through drops in to the mouth allowing for an immune response in the gut. **Ex:** oral polio vaccine, oral typhoid vaccine, oral cholera vaccine, Rotavirus vaccine (RV1 [Rotarix], RV5 [RotaTeq]) is the only

routinely recommended vaccine administered orally. Rotavirus vaccine should never be injected.

When administering a vaccine by injection, choose the correct needle size based on the route, age, patient size, and injection technique.

INTRANASAL ROUTE (NAS): Intranasal vaccine is administered into each nostril using a manufacturer-filled nasal sprayer. **Ex:** Live, attenuated influenza (LAIV [FluMist]) vaccine is the only vaccine administered by the intranasal route.

SUBCUTANEOUS ROUTE (Sub cut):

Subcutaneous injections are administered into the fatty tissue found below the dermis and above muscle tissue. **Ex:** Measles, Mumps, Rubella (MMR), Varicella (chickenpox), Zoster (shingles).

INTRAMUSCULAR ROUTE (IM): This is the most common route, where the vaccine is administered into the muscle through the skin and subcutaneous tissue. It allows for a good absorption of the vaccine. The recommended site is based on age. Use the correct needle length and gauge based on the age, weight, and gender of the recipient. **Ex:** tetanus/diphtheria vaccines.

INTRADERMAL INJECTION: This route involves injecting the vaccine into the dermis, the layer just below the outer skin. It's less commonly used but can be effective for certain vaccines. **Ex:** BCG (for tuberculosis), Some flu vaccines (in clinical trials).

5.METHODOLOGY:

MANUFACTURING OF VACCINE:

The Steps involved in vaccine production as follows.

Step 1: SELECTING THE STRAINS FOR VACCINE PRODUCTION:

- **The seed (strain):** -Manufacturing begins with small amounts of a specific virus (seed).
- Viruse or Bacteria used in manufacture shall be derived from a seed lot system.
- A record of the origin, passage history (including purification and characterisation procedures) and storage conditions should be maintained for each Seed Lot.
- The virus must be free of impurities, including other similar viruses and even variations of the same type of virus.
- The seed must be kept under "ideal" conditions, usually frozen, that prevent the virus from becoming either stronger or weaker than desired.
- Stored in small glass or plastic containers.

Selecting The Seed (Strain):-

- The choice of the seed is depending on a number of factors including the efficacy of the resulting vaccine, and its secondary effects.
- If possible, the bacterial strain or cell line should be obtained from a recognised

culture collection with an established and documented provenance.

- Alternatively, if the chosen vaccine strain is an "in house" clinical isolate, it will be necessary to compile a complete history of the strain, including details of its isolation, identification, and maintenance for product registration.

Step 2: GROWING THE MICRO-ORGANISMS:

METHODS USED FOR GROWING BACTERIA:

- **BATCH CULTURE:** The microbe is grown in a closed vessel. Typically in a test tube or flask.
- **CONTINUOUS CULTURE:** The microbe is grown in vessel which has medium constantly added and spent medium constantly removed. It is performed in a chemostat.

METHODS USED FOR GROWING VIRUSES:

- **CELL (TISSUE) CULTURES:** Cultured cells grow in sheets that support viral replication and permit observation for cytopathic effect.

- **BIRD EMBRYOS:** Incubating egg is an ideal system; virus is injected through the shell.
- **LIVE ANIMAL INOCULATION:** occasionally used when necessary.
- **TRANSGENIC ANIMALS:** Transgenic animals are used as model organisms for testing the safety of vaccines before they are injected into humans. This was conventionally done on monkeys.

Step 3: ISOLATION AND PURIFICATION OF MICRO ORGANISMS:

Product isolation is the removal of those components whose properties vary markedly from that of the desired product. **Purification** selectively separates and retains the desired product at the highest purity per its pre-determined specification. (Remove unwanted compounds). The most common method of vaccine production is based on an initial fermentation process followed by purification as follows

- **CENTRIFUGATION:** Centrifugation is a process by which solid particles are sedimented and separated from a liquid using centrifugal force as a driving force. Centrifugation is used to separation and purification of pathogenic viruse antigens and other agents used in the production of vaccine. Centrifugation is also used to remove dead cells, cell debris etc. Example: Influenza vaccine, rabies vaccine, Hepatitis B vaccine, and Japanese encephalitis vaccine production. Centrifugation methods used for purification are:
 - **DIFFERENTIAL CENTRIFUGATION:** This technique is used for separation of cell organelles and involves different speeds and at different times. Pellet and supernatant obtained as a result are subjected to different speeds at different times, further the supernatant is taken and the process is continued. At low speeds some fractions get separated and small fragments remain in the supernatant.
 - **DENSITY GRADIENT CENTRIFUGATION:** Density gradient centrifugation is a technique that allows the separation of cells, organelles and macromolecules, depending on their size, shape and density.
 - a. Rate zonal centrifugation:** used to separate molecules on the basis of their size, shape and density.
 - b. Isopycnic centrifugation:** a technique used to separate molecules on the basis of density.

(The word "isopycnic" means "equal density".)

- **CHROMATOGRAPHY:** A group of physical separation techniques, which are characterized by the separation of mixtures due to differences in the distribution coefficient of sample components between two phases, one *stationary* and the other mobile phase. *Example:* Modified Vaccine Ankara virus (Small pox vaccine).
 - **Column chromatography:** separates molecules by their chemical and physical differences.
 - **ion exchange chromatography:** separation on basis of charge.
 - **Affinity chromatography-**separation on basis of specific binding sites on the protein.
- **FILTRATION:** Separation of particles from liquid by applying a pressure to the solution to force the solution through a filter. Filtration is classified in two ways.
 - **DEAD END FILTRATION:** All the flows are directed through the membrane with material building up on the surface of filter. (Flow perpendicular to membrane surface). As these particles build up, flow through the filter is quickly reduced and finally it ceases completely. (Causes build-up of filter cake on membrane).
 - **TANGENTIAL FLOW FILTRATION (CROSS FLOW TECHNOLOGY):** During CFF, culture fluid is re-circulated in tangential flow, parallel to the filter membrane. Build-up of viral particles on the membrane is minimised by the recirculation of fluid over the surface, which also facilitates the concentration of particles present in the retained fluid. mainly used in purifying inactivated Arboviral antigen.
 - **ULTRAFILTRATION:** A technique for separating dissolved molecules in solution on the basis of size rating the particles will be retained at the surface of the membrane. During this process the desired proteins and their allied products are separated by their molecular weight, and the volume is reduced thereby increasing the purity considerably compared to the starting volume.

Step 4: INACTIVATION OF ORGANISMS

KILLED/INACTIVATED VACCINE:

➤ **Virus Inactivation:** Viruses can be lipid-coated (enveloped) or non-enveloped. Virus inactivation involves dismantling a virus's ability to infect cells without actually eliminating the virus. Virus inactivation works by one of the following two mechanisms: By attacking the viral envelope or capsid and destroying its ability to infect or interact with cells, By disrupting the viral DNA or RNA and preventing replication as follows

- **Solvent/detergent (S/D) inactivation:**
Effective with lipid-coated viruses. The detergents used in this method, Disrupts the interactions between molecules in the lipid coat rendering the coat dysfunctional and impeding replication. Most enveloped viruses cannot live without their lipid coating, so they die when exposed to these detergents. Other viruses may still live, but they are unable to reproduce, rendering them non-infective. The detergent typically used is Triton-X 100.
- **Pasteurization:**
Effective for both non-lipid and lipid-coated viruses. Because pasteurization involves increasing the temperature of solution to a value that will sufficiently denature the virus. It does not matter whether the virus has an envelope or not because the envelope alone cannot protect the virus from such high temperatures. (at 60 C for 10 hours)
- **Acidic pH inactivation (Low pH Treatment):**
Most effective with lipid-coated viruses. Acidic conditions deactivate virus. Incubation typically occurs at a pH of 4 and lasts anywhere between 6 hours and 21 days.
- **Ultraviolet (UV) inactivation:**
UV rays can be used to inactivate Viruses since virus particles are small and the UV rays can reach the genetic material, inducing the dimerisation of nucleic acids. Once the DNA dimerised, the virus particles cannot replicate their genetic material.

➤ **INACTIVATION BY EXTRACTION**

- **Nucleic acid –**
Nucleic acid is obtained from collected and lysed cells. The nucleic acid is purified by solvent extraction and chromatographic techniques and formulated for the final

vaccine product. Nucleic acid vaccines can be regions of RNA or DNA that code for disease associated proteins.

- **Inclusion bodies-**
Bacterial cells often are used to produce proteins that can function as vaccines. Bacteria produce proteins intracellularly and store the produced proteins in internal structures called inclusion bodies. Following bacterial cell collection and lysis, the inclusion bodies are collected and disrupted. This often involves a series of steps involving protein denaturation followed by protein renaturation or folding. Filtration is employed to achieve clarification of the protein solution during this process.
- **Membrane extraction –**
Vaccine products can be portions of bacterial or mammalian cell membrane structures. These membrane structures are typically protein, but, can be lipid or carbohydrate molecules. The membrane components are usually associated with a disease state. The vaccine product is formulated from the extracted and purified membrane structure.
- **Capsule extraction –**
Some bacteria grow and secrete a complex carbohydrate material forming an external capsule. This capsular material can be isolated and purified to formulate a vaccine. The capsule extraction process usually requires multiple steps of solvent extraction, followed by chromatographic separation or other standard purification techniques.
- **LIVE WHOLE VACCINES:** *Several methods have been used to attenuate viruses for vaccine production.*
 - **Use of a related microorganism from another animal:**
The earliest example was the use of cowpox to prevent smallpox.
 - **Administration of pathogenic or partially attenuated microorganism by an unnatural route**
The virulence of the virus is often reduced when administered by an unnatural route. This principle is used in the immunization of military recruits against adult respiratory distress syndrome rising enterically coated live adenovirus type 4, 7 and (21).

- **Passage of the microorganism in an "unnatural host" or host cell:**

The major vaccines used in man and animals have all been derived this way. After repeated passages, the virus is administered to the natural host. The initial passages are made in healthy animals or in primary cell cultures. There are several examples of this approach: The 17D strain of yellow fever was developed by passage in mice and then in chick embryos, Polioviruses were passaged in monkey kidney cells and measles in chick embryo fibroblasts, Human diploid cells are now widely used such as the WI-38 and MRC-5.

- **Development of temperature sensitive mutants -**

Some strains are attenuated by sudden change in temperature. This method may be used in conjunction with the above method.

Step 5: FORMULATION OF VACCINE: Other than microorganism or its part a vaccine contains the following substance:-

- **Suspending fluids:**

The liquid which contains the chemicals used during production which kill or weaken the organism for use in vaccines. Sterile water, saline or fluids containing protein, Egg proteins are found in influenza and yellow fever vaccines, which are prepared using chicken eggs, Yeast Proteins, Hepatitis B vaccines are made by transfecting cells of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (baker's yeast) with the gene that encodes hepatitis B surface antigen and residual quantities of yeast proteins are contained in the final product.

- **Preservatives and stabilizers:** (the vaccine remain unchanged)

Albumin , phenols, glycine, monosodium glutamate (MSG) and 2-phenoxy - ethanol which are used as stabilisers in a few vaccines to help the vaccine remain unchanged when the vaccine is exposed to heat, light, acidity, or humidity, **Antibiotics**, which are added to some vaccines to prevent the growth of bacteria during production and storage of the vaccine. Antibiotics that are used during vaccine manufacture include neomycin, streptomycin, polymyxin B, chlortetracycline, and amphotericin B, **Thimerosal** is a mercury-containing

preservative that is added to vials of vaccine that contain more than one dose to prevent contamination and growth of potentially harmful bacteria. Eg. diphtheria-tetanus-acellular pertussis (DTaP), hepatitis B, and *Haemophilus influenzae* type B (Hib).

- **Inactivating agents:**

Formaldehyde is used to inactivate bacterial products for toxoid vaccines, (these are vaccines that use an inactive bacterial toxin to produce immunity.), It is also used to kill unwanted viruses and bacteria that might contaminate the vaccine during production, Most formaldehyde is removed from the vaccine before it is packaged, It is used to inactivate influenza virus, poliovirus, and diphtheria and tetanus toxins, β -propiolactone, which is used to inactivate rabies virus, Glutaraldehyde, which is used to inactivate toxins contained in acellular pertussis vaccines.

- **Adjuvants Or Enhancers:** aluminum gels or salts (Alum)

Alum is used in several licensed vaccines including: diphtheria-pertussis-tetanus, diphtheria-tetanus (DT), DT combined with Hepatitis B (HBV), *Haemophilus influenzae* B, Inactivated polio virus, Hepatitis A (HAV), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* vaccine, Meningococcal vaccine, Human papilloma virus (HPV).

Step 6: QUALITY CONTROL AND LOT RELEASE.

- **INCREASE IN VIRULENCE TESTS:**

With live vaccines, there is concern that the organism might be shed from the host and transmitted to contact animals, causing disease if it retains residual virulence or reverts to virulence. All live vaccines should be tested for virulence by means of passage studies.

- **ASSESSING RISK TO THE ENVIRONMENT :**

The ability of each live vaccine to shed, to spread to contact target and non-target animals, and to persist in the environment must be evaluated to provide information for assessing the risk of the vaccine to the environment, taking into account human health.

- **INTERFERENCE TESTS:**

For products with two or more antigenic components, tests must confirm that there

is no interference between individual components, that is, one component causing a decrease in the protective immunological response to another component.

- **CONSISTENCY OF PRODUCTION:**

Prior to marketing approval of any new product, each establishment should produce in its facilities three consecutive production batches/serials of completed product to evaluate the consistency of production.

- **STABILITY TEST:**

Stability studies (based on an acceptable potency test) are required to establish the validity of the expiry date that appears on the product package.

LOT RELEASE.

Batch/serial release for distribution

:Prior to release, the manufacturer must test each batch/serial for purity, safety, and potency.

1. Batch/serial purity test: Purity is determined by testing for a variety of contaminants. Tests to detect contaminants are performed on: master seeds, primary cells, MCSs (Master cell stock), ingredients of animal origin if not subjected to sterilisation (e.g. fetal bovine serum, bovine albumin, or trypsin), and each batch of final product prior to release.

2. Batch/serial safety test: Batches are considered satisfactory if local and systemic reactions to vaccination with the batch to be released are in line with those described in the registration dossier and product literature.

3. /serial potency test: Batch/serial potency tests. required for each batch prior to release, are designed to correlate with the host animal vaccination challenge efficacy **Batch** studies.

OTHER TESTS:- Depending on the form of vaccine being produced, certain tests may be indicated.

These tests may concern: The level of moisture contained in desiccated products, The level of residual inactivate in killed products, The complete inactivation of killed products, pH, The level of preservatives and permitted antibiotics, Physical stability of adjuvant, Retention of vacuum in desiccated products, A general physical examination of the final vaccine.

6. SAMPLING and LABELLING

- Samples should be selected from each batch/serial of product.
- The selector should pick representative sample.
- Standards for labelling products will vary from country to country.

7. FIELD TEST (safety and efficacy).

In preclinical stage the vaccine is first tested in animals for safety and efficacy, followed by clinical studies conducted in four phase stages.

8. PERFORMANCE MONITORING:

- Side effects are common after getting a vaccine. These can include:
- Pain, redness, or swelling where the vaccine was given.
- Tiredness or headache.
- Fever and chills.
- Muscle or joint soreness.
- Nausea, vomiting, or diarrhoea.
- Fussiness, crying, restlessness, or decreased appetite in infants
- After the MMR or chickenpox (varicella) vaccine: fever, rash, or other side effects (including swelling of glands in the cheeks or neck after the MMR vaccine) may occur one to two weeks after immunization.
- After the nasal spray influenza (flu) vaccine: nasal congestion and runny nose

Signs of a severe allergic reaction can include: Difficulty breathing, Swelling of your face and throat, A fast heartbeat, A bad rash all over your body, Dizziness and weakness.

TABLE:1 VACCINATION SCHEDULE FOR PREGNANT WOMEN.

vaccine	When to give	dose	Route	site
For pregnant women:				
T T-1	Early in pregnancy	0.5ml	Intra-muscular	Upper arm
T T-2	4 weeks after TT-1	0.5ml	Intra-muscular	Upper arm
T T-BOOSTER	If received 2 TT doses in a pregnancy within the last 3yrs.	0.5ml	Intra-muscular	Upper arm

TABLE:2 VACCINATION SCHEDULE FOR INFANTS.

vaccine	When to give	dose	Route	site
For infants:				
BCG	At birth or as early as possible till one year of age.	0.1ml	Intradermal	Left upper arm
Hepatitis B-birth dose	At birth or as early as possible within 24 hours.	0.5ml	Intramuscular	Antero-lateral side of mid thigh
OPV-0	At birth or as early as possible within the first 15 days.	2 drops	Oral	Oral
OPV1,2 and 3	At 6 weeks, 10 weeks,15 weeks (OPV can be given till 5 years of age)	2 drops	Oral	Oral
Pentavalent 1,2 and 3	At 6 weeks, 10 weeks,15 weeks (can be given till one year of age)	0.5ml	Intramuscular	Antero-lateral side of mid thigh
Rotavirus	At 6 weeks, 10 weeks,15 weeks (can be given till one year of age)	5 drops	Oral	Oral
IPV	Two fractional doses at 6 and 14 weeks of age	0.1 ml	Intra dermal two fractional dose	Intra-dermal:right upper arm
Measles/MR 1st doses	9 completed moths-12 months. (can be given till five years of age)	0.5 ml	Subcutaneous	Right upper arm
JE-1	9 completed moths-12 months.	0.5 ml	Subcutaneous	Left upper arm
Vitamin-A (1st dose)	At 9 completed months with measles-rubella.	1ml	oral	oral

TABLE:3 VACCINATION SCHEDULE FOR CHILDREN.

vaccine	When to give	dose	Route	site
For children:				
DPT booster-1	16-24 months	0.5 ml	Intra-muscular	Antero- lateral side of mid thigh
Measles/M R2nd doses	16-24 months	0.5ml	Sub –cutaneous	Right upper arm
Opv booster	16-24 months	2 drops	oral	Oral
JE-2	16-24 months	0.5ml	Sub-cutaneous	Left upper arm
VITAMIN A(2nd to 9th dose)	16-18 months. then one dose every 6 months up to the age of 5 years.	2ml	oral	oral
DPT BOOSTER- 2	5-6 years	0.5 ml	Intra-muscular	Upper arm
TT	10 years and 16 years	0.5 ml	Intra-muscular	Upper arm

10. CONCLUSION:

In order to provide immunity against infectious diseases, vaccinations are an essential public health strategy that use biological preparations. With the invention of Edward Jenner's smallpox vaccine in the 18th century, vaccine research has advanced dramatically, giving rise to a variety of vaccine forms, including recombinant, inactivated, and live attenuated shots. A number of procedures are involved in the production process, such as strain selection, microbe growth, purification, inactivation, and formulation. Strict quality control measures are taken to ensure product safety and effectiveness. Schedules for vaccinations are designed to improve community immunity and stop disease outbreaks for a variety of populations, including infants and pregnant women. All things considered, vaccinations continue to be essential for maintaining global health.

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